

Cost reduction of floating wind technology

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Background

The COREWIND project aims at strengthening European leadership in floating offshore wind energy. The project partners are collaborating to increase the competitiveness of the technology through the optimisation of mooring and anchoring systems, as well as dynamic cables. This will allow enhanced performance and significant cost reductions.

The project provides recommendations on best design practices, as well as open data models to accelerate the development of concrete-based semi-submersible and spar floating structures.

A part of the project will focus on testing the recommended innovative designs and optimisation parameters in two concrete-based floater concepts (semi-sub and spar).

The resulting recommendations are expected to facilitate the development of floating offshore wind energy, reducing risks and uncertainties and contributing to lower LCOE (levelised cost of energy) estimates.

COREWIND activities and publications are free and publicly available. To find out more visit our webpage and follow us on Twitter and LinkedIn.

Objectives

- Innovative design and optimisation of station keeping systems and dynamic cables
- Optimisation of operations and maintenance strategies and installation techniques
- Experimental testing
- LCOE reduction
- Standardisation, commercialisation and exploitation

Project coordinator

Project partners

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